

Deliverable D10.5

Gender Action Plan

Deliverable report

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Table of contents

Deliverable report	3
Document Contributors	3
Document History	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of contents	5
List of Abbreviations	7
1 Executive Summary	8
2 INTRODUCTION	9
2.1 Project objectives	10
2.2 Deliverable structure	10
2.3 Challenges	10
2.4 Definitions and concepts	11
3 Gender management/Action plans	12
3.1 Introduction	12
3.2 Guidelines: steps to ensure the success of the development of a GAP	12
3.3 Most common risks and methods to avoid them	13
3.4 Gender Action Plan development phases	14
4 Auditing/analysis: gender dimension in the implementation of technological solutions	15
5 Auditing/analysis: gender dimension in the Pilots	17
5.1 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in Spain	17
5.2 Data on gender in the aggregates sector in Spain	18
5.3 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in Italy	19
5.4 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in Germany	20
5.5 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in Portugal	20
5.6 Data on gender in the aggregates sector in Portugal	21
5.7 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in France	22
5.8 Gender in the aggregates sector in France	22
6 DEQ Gender Action plan	23
6.1 Gender dimension in research	23
6.1.1 Actions/objectives to implement in DEQ to ensure gender dimension in research	24
6.1.2 Gender balance in research	25
7 DEQ GENDER EQUALITY PLAN	27

7.1	Principles and objectives	27
7.2	Actions	28
7.3	Tools for measuring compliance with the equality plan	29
7.3.1	Skills of the members involved in the DEQ project	29
7.3.2	Gender policy in place	30
7.3.3	Summary	31
8	Conclusions	33
9	References	35
	List of Figures	36
	List of Tables	37

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
CIG	The Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality
CSE	Social and Economic Committee
DoA	Description of Action
EB	Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
GA	Grant Agreement
GAP	Gender Action Plan
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IFS	Individual Financial Statement
IQS	Innovative Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
PFSIGN	Project Financial Statement
PRC	Project Research Committee
RP	Reporting Period
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable is related to Task 10.4 “Data Management Plan and Gender Action Plan and Monitoring”, which deals with the implementation of the evaluation and monitorization of Gender in the project, as part of H2020 principles.

The Gender action plan & monitoring, GAP, is key for companies’ participation to other future European projects.

Integrating sex and gender analysis into Research and Innovation (R&I) adds value to research and is therefore crucial to secure Europe’s leadership in science and technology, and to support its inclusive growth.

The strengthening of the integration of the gender dimension into R&I is one of the gender equality priorities set for Horizon Europe. The gender dimension cuts across all aspects of Horizon Europe and contributes to numerous steps in the R&I cycle, considering the needs of women, men, and gender diverse individuals as end-users of technological innovations.

European Commission’s requirements and recommendations on Gender Equality Plans will be studied to establish the master lines that should structure and guide the DEQ Gender Action Plan (GAP).

Once the literature and the best practices have been studied, a gender dimension study within the project will be carried out, analysing those aspects that can be improved.

Once this analysis is done, the Plan will be developed, setting the objectives, the specific activities that will be carried out for its achievement and the indicators that will allow to measure and evaluate the level of success and fulfilment of the Plan.

The DEQ Gender Management Plan will analyse the gender dimension and propose measures regarding:

- Gender dimension throughout research: gender impact within the European aggregates sector and in the field of technological development and ICT solutions will be analysed.
- Measures to ensure gender-balanced research team: decision-making process and total number of workers involved in research teams.

At the end of the deliverable, a series of annexes will be included.

2 INTRODUCTION

Ever since the Treaty of Rome, the European Union has consistently advocated gender equality as one of its core policies. Despite the efforts to promote gender in research, women remain under-represented, and the issue of gender is far from being systematically addressed in research projects.

Investing in equal opportunities for men and women in research results in teams better performing and attracts top-level researchers. Similarly, investing in a gender-sensitive approach to the research content makes for higher quality and validity.

Gender equality is a core value of the EU and a universally recognised human right, as well as an imperative to well-being, economic growth, prosperity, good governance, peace, and security. All people, in all their diversity, should be free to live their chosen life, thrive socially and economically, participate, and take a lead as equals.

Nowadays, three objectives underpin the EC's activities on gender equality in H2020. They are in line with the European Research Area (ERA) Communication of July 2012:

- Foster gender balance in H2020 research teams.
- Ensure gender balance in decision-making processes.
- Integrate gender/sex analysis in research and innovation (R&I).

Gender equality concerns all parts of Horizon 2020. All Horizon 2020 funded projects, are encouraged to promote gender balance at all levels in their teams and in their management structures. The Commission has introduced new measures to strengthen gender equality in Horizon Europe, such as the requirement of a gender equality plan from applicants.

The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.

The DIGIECOQUARRY INNOVATIVE DIGITAL SUSTAINABLE AGGREGATES SYSTEMS, DEQ, is a Horizon Europe Project funded by the EC. It aims to design, develop, and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) that comprises sensors, processes, tools and data capture, processing, and exchange methods to provide integrated, digitized information, control of automatic and real-time processes for aggregate quarries.

Even though when stating the objectives of the project, it could be concluded that it is an issue in which the gender dimension is irrelevant, from the project's conception, the gender dimension has been considered as one of its fundamental elements.

Only through an intersectional methodology, including a Gender Plan, can valuable and socially relevant results be achieved.

According to the article 33 of the DEQ Grant Agreement:

“ARTICLE 33 — GENDER EQUALITY

33.1 Obligation to aim for gender equality.

The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.

33.2 Consequences of non-compliance.

If a beneficiary breaches its obligations under this Article, the Agency may apply any of the measures described in Chapter 6.”

With this commitment, the project includes within its tasks, 10.4 "Gender Management Plan", which will be developed in this deliverable.

2.1 Project objectives

The objective of this deliverable is to develop the Gender Management Plan for the DEQ Project, in accordance with the requirements and recommendations published by the European Commission.

This Gender Management Plan will be divided into two key elements: on one hand, actions to ensure gender balance within the research teams and within the decision making process; on the other hand, the gender dimension in the research, analysing the influence that sex or gender may have on the implementation of technological solutions in the aggregates sector, identifying problems related to discrimination or prejudice on the basis of gender, seeking solutions to the problems identified and establishing evaluation and monitoring systems for the proposed solutions.

2.2 Deliverable structure

This deliverable will be divided into the following chapters:

"Chapter 2: Introduction": This is an introductory chapter defining the structure of the deliverable, the basic concepts of gender, and the challenges identified in the project when elaborating a Gender Action Plan.

"Chapter 3: Gender Action Plans": deals with the subject of Gender Action Plans from a general point of view, referring to the steps to be followed, basic structure phases, main risks that can be encountered and ways to avoid them.

The initial step of any gender plan requires a situation analysis or audit in which the gender issue is reflected within the object of study. Therefore, **chapters 4 and 5** will address the issue of gender impact in the technology development sector and in the aggregates sector, focusing the analysis on the gender situation in the aggregates sector in the countries where the pilots will be carried out, i.e., Spain, Portugal, France, Italy and Germany.

The **"Chapter 6: Gender Action Plan in DEQ"**, will develop the structure of the GAP. The DEQ Gender Equality Plan, is included in **Chapter 7** with a series of measurement instruments or indicators to monitor and evaluate its fulfilment.

"Chapter 8, Conclusions ".

2.3 Challenges

Gender equality plans and gender management plans are relatively new concepts that are constantly changing and evolving. A research effort on the best practices available has been made for the development of this Gender Management Plan.

The female presence within the aggregates sector (Figure 1) is rare and mostly reduced to administrative or management positions. In most cases, companies will not have gender equality plans and there will not be awareness of their usefulness or necessity.

In this scenario, the construction of this Gender Management Plan, in addition to being a challenge, becomes an opportunity, insofar as the female role in mining can be analysed in different pilot scenarios throughout Europe and solutions can be proposed to improve gender dimension, resulting in benefits for the sector.

Moreover, while we may consider the COVID-19 pandemic to be practically over, its effects go far beyond the disease itself. It has changed the way we relate to each other, the way we work and develop study and research processes, the way companies manage security and access to facilities, so that in order to ensure that sufficient and valid results are available for research, the preferred option has been to use measures and tools that can be used online, avoiding travel and limitations or problems of access to either the pilots or the research teams.

Figure 1 Women miners in quarries.

2.4 Definitions and concepts

Sex: sex refers to the biologically determined characteristics of men and women in terms of reproductive organs and functions based on chromosomal complement and physiology.

Gender: gender refers to the social construction of women and men, of femininity and masculinity, which varies in time and place, and between cultures.

Gender Equality: refers to the situation where individuals of both sexes are free to develop their personal abilities and make choices without the limitations imposed by strict gender roles. Is a core value of the EU and a universally recognised Human Right.

Gender Equity: is the process of being fair to someone regardless of their sex or gender. To ensure fairness, measures must be taken to compensate for cumulative economic, social, and political disadvantages based on sex or gender that prevent someone from operating on a level playing field.

Gender Mainstreaming: is the process of incorporating a gender perspective into policies, strategies, programs, project activities, and administrative functions, as well as into the institutional culture of an organization.

Gender Gap: is a measure of gender inequality. It is a useful social development indicator.

Gender Stereotype: is a generalised view or preconception about attributes, or characteristics that are or ought to be possessed by women and men or the roles that are or should be performed by men and women.

Intersectionality: is an analytical framework for understanding how aspects of a person's social and political identities combine to create different modes of discrimination and privilege. Intersectionality identifies multiple factors of advantage and disadvantage, as for example: gender, cast, sex, race, class, sexuality, religion, disability, physical appearance, and height.

Equal opportunities for women and men: equal opportunity indicates the absence of barriers to economic, political, and social participation on the grounds of sex. It should be distinguished from equal treatment, which merely implies avoiding direct discrimination.

Gender integration: strategies applied in programmatic design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation to take gender considerations into account and compensate for gender-based inequalities.

Gender-sensitive research: in gender-sensitive research, gender is consistently considered throughout the research cycle.

Gender-specific research: it focuses on gender itself as a subject matter.

Gender-blind research: it does not take gender into account, based on the often-incorrect assumption that possible differences between men and women are not relevant for the research at hand.

Gender bias: is the often unintentional and implicit differentiation between men and women by placing one gender in a hierarchical position relative to the other in a certain context, because of stereotypical images of masculinity and femininity.

Gender norms: spoken and unspoken rules produced through social institutions, such as the family and workplace, and cultural products such as technology and social media.

Gender identity: refers to how individuals and groups perceive and present themselves in relation to gender norms.

Gender relations: refers to how individuals interact with other people and institutions in specific sociocultural contexts.

3 Gender management/Action plans

3.1 Introduction

The demands on the gender dimension in Horizon Europe have undergone an evolution with respect to those established for H2020 projects.

The gender dimension becomes a default requirement throughout the program, especially regarding research groups and the decision-making process. Special funding is established for the case of inclusive gender programs, gender studies and intersectional research.

The GAP stands as a tool a tool for sustainable change towards fairer working conditions and a more inclusive environment.

In addition, it makes the quality of HR management more transparent, avoiding situations of harassment or "inbreeding". It is correlated with excellence in research and its innovative potential.

Even though the requirement that there be a GAP in force is only mandatory to Public Bodies or higher education institutions, from the DEQ Project, in the conviction that only in a research process that involves the gender dimension, socially relevant results can be achieved, and in accordance with article 33 of our GA, we develop a Gender Management Plan in accordance with the Commission's recommendations.

3.2 Guidelines: steps to ensure the success of the development of a GAP

Gender dimension analysis: a deep knowledge of the gender dimension from the point of view of the research process and in relation to the research object should be carried out. It is essential that the greatest amount of data is available.

Support from the management of the project to the GAP, from the decision-making bodies: this support must be shown internally, facilitating the development of the GAP as much as possible, but also externally, through public statements (articles, intervention in congresses or meetings talking about the GAP, publications on the project's website, etc.).

Gender Equality Officer: appointment of a person in charge of gender equality in the project, a Gender Equality Officer, with specific training in this matter.

Awareness and training strategy: development of a communication, information, negotiation, and awareness strategy on the gender dimension.

Calendar: enough time for the development of the analysis or audit phase.

Participation of the people involved in the project: development strategy that favours the joint participation of all members of the consortium. It is a substantial part of the success of the project. The Plan, with its objectives and proposed measures, must be presented to all members of the consortium in a phase prior to its implementation, allowing a co-creative approach, so that we raise awareness in the members of the project of participation in the GAP, considering it as their own.

Clear objectives: establishment of clear objectives, targets, and measures, as well as precise indicators for their monitoring and evaluation.

Resources: sufficient funding for the development of the GAP.

Sustainability: implementation of the GAP, taking advantage of and integrating it into the processes and documents already developed, in accordance with the strategic objectives of the project.

Flexibility: build the GAP in a flexible way, so that it can be adapted to changes.

Challenges strategy: establish a strategy to face obstacles or resistance that may be found in its application or development.

3.3 Most common risks and methods to avoid them

Using gender stereotypes: the objectives of the project and the data collected should be analysed even when it may seem that the influence of gender is minimal or non-existent, to detect if the researcher has been influenced by a gender stereotype in the treatment of the data. To avoid this, in data collection and experimental design, “naive” experimenters should be used (i.e., experimenters uninformed about predictions, treatments, and sex of the organism), whenever possible, to avoid introducing bias. This is especially important in behavioural studies, where observers may carry unconscious assumptions about expected male or female behaviours. Also, we should be aware that, when collecting data, researchers may pay more attention to findings that confirm what they believe to be true.

Sex/gender taken as binary categories: gender/sex is traditionally viewed as binary, with people falling into one of two categories: male or female. This view of gender/sex has started to evolve challenged by a variety of individual and cultural changes including the implementation of gender-inclusive language and gender-neutral pronouns such as “they”¹, official state policies recognizing a third sex (e.g., in Germany)², and visibility of individuals with expressions of gender/sex that fall outside the binary³.

Not considering other categories of possible influence: in this sense, it is essential to apply intersectionality. When designing an experiment, arguments should be presented for a chosen design, especially when only one sex/gender is studied or when the methods differ for gex/gender. This will allow the readers to assess whether the design embeds gender-biased assumptions. Where feasible, measure the same parameters in the same way in all sexes. If only one sex/gender is studied, we should **specify which and provide the rationale for why**.

Assigning differences automatically to sex (taking sex for gender).

Overaccentuating of sex and/or gender differences without having proof of their role in the researched topic.

Overlooking proofs of minimal or no differences (sex and/or gender).

Uncareful generalizations: when generalizing results, scientific rigor should be applied to:

- ensure representative sampling of the sexes.
- unbiased trait measurements.
- evaluation of alternative hypotheses.

Language Usage Unawareness: we should be aware of and be careful in the choice of words, metaphors, and anthropomorphic terminology in relation to sex, as they may carry normative implications and may mislead a reader into gender-biased assumptions. Descriptive, neutral, and operational language should be used. If the meaning of the sentence is changed beyond the simple change of sex, the wording may be gender biased.

1 Boylan, J. F. (2018, January 9). That’s what ze said. The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/>

2 Eddy, M., Bennett, J. (2017, November 8). Germany must allow third gender category, court rules. The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/>

3 Steinmetz. (2014, May 29). The transgender tipping points. Time. <https://time.com/135480/transgender-tipping-point/>

3.4 Gender Action Plan development phases

For the development of a Gender Action Plan, it will be necessary to go through the following phases (see Figure 2):

- A previous Auditing or analysis phase, in which the gender dimension of the project will be analysed, existing gender biases will be detected both in the subject under investigation and in the sector in which the specific technological solutions will be implemented. Also in this phase, a detailed study of gender balance should be made in the research teams and the decision-making process.
- Once we have an image that is as close as possible to the reality of the gender dimension in terms of the object of research and referring to the research process itself, the GAP's design and planning phase will be established, which will be structured according to the following:
 - Objectives
 - Measures/activities.
 - Indicators/impact.
 - Target Groups.
 - Timeline.
 - Division of responsibilities.
 - Budget.
- Once the design of the GAP is clear, it will be implemented in accordance with the objectives, indicators, and established activities.
- The plan implementation process will last 2 to 3 years. Periodically, preferably every year, the effectiveness of the plan must be evaluated, monitoring the evolution of the indicators that have been considered in accordance with the set objectives, so that it can be determined whether the proposed activities have made it possible to reach the set objectives. Therefore, as the implementation phase progresses, we will carry out an evaluation and monitoring task of the plan.
- Once the first period of validity has elapsed, the process must be repeated, going again through each of the phases.

Figure 2 DEQ GAP phases.

4 Auditing/analysis: gender dimension in the implementation of technological solutions

The gender dimension in innovation, technology and entrepreneurship is a novel research area that has been little explored in the literature.

While there is a wealth of studies on the participation of women in science, especially academic science⁴, women's presence, identities, and advancement in innovation and technology-related professions, such as technology transfer and entrepreneurship, are only little documented. UNESCO warns that women are under-represented in (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics): only 29% of researchers worldwide are women.

When dealing with gender biases in technological research and the implementation of technological solutions, it can be considered that the situation is one of "**gender blindness**" due to the lack of visibility of the individual innovator.

Innovation is not gender-blind, but rather inherently **gender-biased**, because of an implicit, socially constructed assumption that women are less innovative than men as a function of traditional gender relations, that men-dominated industries/sectors are more innovative than women-dominated ones, all rooted in a social perception of technology that is more often associated to men than to women.

From this perspective, it also appears that "competition" is often associated with the male-gendered cultural element of the innovation process, while "consensus-building" appears to be a more feminine approach.

⁴ Xie and Shauman, 2003; Smith-Doerr, 2004; Sonnert and Holton, 2006.

A similar situation is found in technology, with women concentrated at the low pay, hands-on product making end and men at the opposite end of high pay and creative design⁵. Paradoxically, new technologies offer new employment opportunities for women, but also work against them, keeping them confined to the lower, semi-skilled or unskilled positions, in the attempt to reduce the threat of women's entry into the men's sphere of work and preserve the masculine orientation towards work⁶.

In general, male domination of technology and engineering was found to be result of a triple effect:

- male dominance in most technology and engineering fields, both numerically and in leadership positions.
- processes of homosociality, inclusion and exclusion in both the control, gatekeeping and decision-making on excellence, and the award of excellence itself.
- and the increasing internationalization of networks, organizations and institutions that introduce social gendered relations at the local, national, disciplinary, and professional levels.

Male dominance in technology not only blocks women's access to the better and higher paid jobs, but also has broader consequences that go beyond workforce structure, introducing biases in areas like health or leading to the creation of technologies that are useful from a male perspective, but fail to address important issues for women users. Moreover, technologies may sometimes be selected to support a male-gendered social structure even though they are less productive⁷. This is consistent with the perception of a public sphere, with visible male roles in the production of technological innovation, along with a private sphere with obscure female support roles in the utilization of technology.

A gender gap in venture creation and ownership activity has been observed across the globe for both early-stage entrepreneurial participation and established business ownership, and is greatest in the high-income country group, regardless of type of activity. In the high-income group, men are almost twice as likely to be early stage or established business owners than women⁸. On the one hand, an often-evoked reason for women's lower likelihood to initiate new enterprises is their lower self-confidence than men's. On the other hand, it has been shown that banks, venture capitalists or business angels are less likely to support female-initiated enterprises.

Therefore, what appears to be a lack of confidence in women may be a realistic appraisal of reduced chances for success. This may explain to a large extent women's unwillingness to be entrepreneurial or at least the tendency to wait until higher level of resources have been achieved before taking the entrepreneurial plunge.

However, recent years have seen a variety of top-down and bottom-up efforts that carried with them the seeds of change and made some progress in re-ordering the relationship of women and men to technological innovation.

The traditional gendered nature of science and technology thus seems to have gradually evolved towards more gender equal formats, as specific steps have been taken to introduce women's needs into the problem choice arena, as many women's wish to balance the professional and the personal have been recognized and as inequalities in distribution of resources available for women's technological projects are at least attempted to be redressed.

For example, the pervasive spread of ICTs helped narrow the digital divide between men and women, facilitated women's work from home and gave a new impetus to the creation of female-owned businesses⁹.

The gender dimension in innovation, technology and entrepreneurship cuts across and raises new issues for research and policymaking in several related areas, such as organizational change, human resources, and sustainable development.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and related professions have been much trumpeted to have a great potential to create new employment opportunities for women.

⁵ Rosser, 2006

⁶ Cockburn, 1983.

⁷ Bray, 1997.

⁸ GEM, 2006.

⁹ UN-ECE, 2004. Available at: <http://www.unece.org/gender/documents/Overview.pdf>

Exploring the gendering in technology and engineering research has become a key issue on the agenda of European policy-makers due to the strong position this field enjoys in national, European, and international research policy and because it continues to be the most male-dominated research field. Current attempts to promote scientific excellence in Europe can no longer ignore the gender aspects of research organizations, managers, programmes, policies, and outcomes.

The combination of scientific excellence with the promotion of gender equality has become a central challenge for gender-sensitive science and research policy. Mainstreaming gender equality has been introduced in many countries as an instrument to reduce or remove gender bias, through measures to integrate gender equality into all policy areas, scrutinizing social constructions of gender and their implications for women and men respectively.

Recommendations are made to improve women's participation by broadening recruitment from academia, where the proportion of women in high positions is low, to industry and government.

5 Auditing/analysis: gender dimension in the Pilots

The Extractive Industry is a major economic driver for many countries. It creates jobs, provides for essential materials, and creates opportunities for growth and development.

While the extractive industry creates jobs, there are significant gender disparities in male and female access to jobs.

Working on the simple assumption that men and women are equally and similarly impacted by EI, and overlooking key variations and differences, can result in isolating and overburdening women. Although many companies have a strong commitment to sustainable development and social investment in the communities in which they operate, failure to understand how Extractive Industries impact different groups in the community can undermine these commitments, with costs to the efficiency and sustainability of operations themselves.

An interesting starting point for the research to be carried out in the project is the number of people of different genders in the European aggregates sector and its evolution or trend as well as the nature of the positions occupied mostly by one gender or the other.

However, when collecting data on gender differences in the aggregates sector in the different countries under study, we have encountered difficulties in finding quality official data in all countries.

This lack or difficulty in obtaining gender data yields a first result or significant data on gender impact. It may arise from a lack of culture or awareness regarding the statistical importance of including the gender perspective in official statistics. It may also lead us to conclude that the presence of people of a gender other than male in the extractive industry sector is very low, so low that it may even be considered irrelevant for statistical purposes.

In any case, in all European states under study, there is a concern in relation to the gender issue, and equal opportunities, which translates into a series of instruments, tools and legislative and organizational measures, to achieve equality, effective for everyone.

In this chapter, an analysis will be made of the gender situation and the regulatory and institutional framework in relation to gender equality in each of the DEQ pilot countries, i.e., Spain, France, Italy, Portugal and Germany. In addition, gender data on the aggregates sector will be analysed in those countries for which official statistical quality data have been obtained.

5.1 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in Spain

Gender Equality plans normative is born from the approval of the Organic Law of Effective Equality of Women and Men 3/2007 (LOI), which in its explanatory memorandum alludes to the right to equality of Spaniards before the law without prevailing any discrimination based on race, sex, religion, opinion or any other personal or social condition or circumstance, enshrined in article 14 of the Spanish Constitution.

In addition, in its article 35 the Constitution states that all Spaniards have the duty to work and the right to work, to free choice of profession or trade, to promotion through work and to sufficient remuneration to satisfy their needs and those of their families, without under any discrimination based on sex.

Equality is one of the fundamental values or pillars on which Spanish rule of law is built on. It is also a fundamental principle of the European Union to protect and defend said principle and to achieve its effective achievement in Spanish society.

The right to equal pay between women and men for the same work or work of equal value is a founding principle of the European Union enshrined in the Treaty of Rome of 1957. Later, the requirement to guarantee this equality in pay was embodied in Article 157 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union and in the Directive on the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment between men and women in matters of employment and occupation.

After the approval of Royal Decree Law 6/2019, there has been an extension in the obligation to have equality plans to a greater number of companies, so that this requirement will become effective gradually for companies with more than 50 workers within a period of three years from March 7, 2019, compared to those of more than 250 workers set previously.

In any case, considering the average size of aggregates companies in Spain, most companies have a workforce of between 10-15 workers, or even less, which leads us to the fact that most of them do not reach the limit of 50 workers established by Spanish law to make it mandatory to have an equality plan.

5.2 Data on gender in the aggregates sector in Spain

Consulted the data of the extractive industry sector in Spain, the absolute value of women hired in the extractive sector with respect to that of men in the first quarter of 2021 was 3.7. During the second quarter of 2021, the number rose to 4.6 (see Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Regarding the percentages, in the first quarter there were 0.09% of women hired compared to men and 0.1% in the second quarter of 2021.

Figure 3 Active Population Survey (EPA) Source, National Institute of Statistics. SPAIN 2021.

Figure 4 Gender evolution in mining. Source Mining Statistics 2017.

In the aggregates sector, direct employment amounts to 8 813 workers, to which must be added a further 15 255 indirect workers, for a total of 24 064 workers, according to the data from the Mining Statistics of Spain (2020)¹⁰. The total increase in employment is estimated at +4.51%. The sector directly employs 850 women, 9.65% of total direct employment.

5.3 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in Italy

The general principle of equality between women and men has been enshrined in Article 3 of the Italian Constitution: ‘All citizens have equal social dignity and are equal before the law, without distinction of sex, race, language, religion, political opinion, personal and social conditions.’

Legislative Decree No. 198 of 2006 established the National Code of Equal Opportunities between Women and Men and is considered the Italian legal framework for gender equality and women’s empowerment. The Code assembles 11 laws on equal opportunities in a single text, intending to rationalise and harmonise the current legislative provisions on gender equality and regulating the promotion of equal opportunities between women and men in the areas of ethical, social, and economic relations, and civil and political rights. It also introduced the principle of gender mainstreaming, obliging the government to consider a gender perspective.

In July 2021, Italy adopted an overall strategy focused on gender equality, ‘the National Strategy for Gender Equality’ (Strategia nazionale per la parità di genere). The National Strategy specifically promotes measures for the integration of a gender perspective in all areas of social and economic life, and policy, and for the dissemination of suitable tools to allow for the assessment of the impacts of public policies from a gender perspective (gender budget).

In addition to the National Strategy, there are sectoral laws on specific aspects of gender equality in place.

Italy’s main government equality body is the Department for Equal Opportunities (Dipartimento per le pari opportunità, DEO) of the Italian Presidency of the Council of Ministers (since 1996).

The independent gender equality body in Italy is the National Equality Counsellor (Consigliera nazionale di parità).

The law requires public and private entities with more than 50 employees to submit a report on the gender balance of their personnel. Based on the analysis of these submitted reports, the public administration prepares a report on the status of gender balance at work every two years.

¹⁰ Mining Statistics of Spain; <https://energia.gob.es/mineria/Estadistica/Paginas/Consulta.aspx>

5.4 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in Germany

German constitutional law stresses the equality of men and women and expresses a federal commitment to an active and effective equality policy. The state promotes the actual enforcement of the equality between men and women and works towards the elimination of existing disadvantages.

Recent laws on gender equality in the labour market and public administration include a 'Federal Law on Pay Transparency' (Entgelttransparenzgesetz), a law to increase the share of women in leadership positions (Zweites Führungspositionen-Gesetz - FüPoG II), and a law to promote 'Women in STEM professions'.

The principle of gender equality is enshrined in other laws, several more federal laws concerning aspects of gender equality across economic sectors have recently been adopted.

Gender equality should be ensured, secured, and promoted in all the government's political, administrative and agenda-setting measures (federal and regional). The country's first (2011), second (2017) and third (2021) Gender Equality Reports (Gleichstellungsbericht) further underline gender mainstreaming as an important tool for gender equality – but also highlight ongoing challenges concerning leadership and cross-sectoral implementation of gender equality.

In the 2018 Coalition Treaty, the federal government sought to respond to these challenges by creating a 'cross-sectoral equality strategy' for all policy areas and a gender equality action plan. The Federal Equality Strategy

(Gleichstellungsstrategie) sets out 9 goals ensuring economic independence for everyone; establishing care professions as attractive career paths; setting standards for the digital world; making paid work and unpaid care work reconcilable; bringing more women into economic leadership positions; establishing equal participation in democracy; eliminating stereotypes in culture and science; strengthening gender equality in public administration; and making gender equality a task for the entire government.

The main governmental equality body is the Division for Gender Equality within the Ministry of Family Affairs, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth (Abteilung 'Gleichstellung', Bundesministerium für Familien, Senioren, Frauen und Jugend – BMFSFJ). This Division conducts research on gender equality issues, in addition to publishing and disseminating information on gender equality for public information and training. It is also responsible for integrating gender equality considerations into Germany's EU and international affairs.

5.5 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in Portugal

Portugal's 1976 Constitution enshrines the principle of equality in Articles 9 (Fundamental task of the state) and 13 (Principle of equality). It has a highly developed policy and legal framework to implement gender mainstreaming through The Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality (CIG), an inter-ministerial structure of Counsellors for Equality and municipal structure of local equality advisors/counsellors, and obligations on gender budgeting and impact assessments.

In 1997, the Global Plan for Equal Opportunities (Resolution of Council of Ministers 49/97) gave greater prominence to the integration of a gender perspective at all policy levels. The primary objective of the Global Plan was to integrate the principle of equal opportunities for women and men into all economic, social, and cultural policies.

Portugal does not have an overarching law exclusively focused on gender equality, but in addition to being clearly established in the Portuguese Constitution, the principle of gender equality was extended to the entire Portuguese legal system.

The current National Strategy on Equality and Non-discrimination (the Estratégia Nacional para a Igualdade e a Não Discriminação 2018-2030 «Portugal + Igual»; the ENIND)[4] was implemented in 2018 and will remain in force until 2030. The Strategy is now closely aligned to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), has a longer-term perspective and aims to involve almost all ministries.

There are two governmental bodies responsible for the promotion of gender equality in Portugal. The first is the Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality (CIG, Comissão para a Cidadania e a Igualdade de Género); the second governmental body responsible for the promotion of gender equality in Portugal is the Commission for Equality in Labour

and Employment (CITE; Comissão para a Igualdade no Trabalho e no Emprego). Every year, CIG publishes the document “Gender equality in Portugal”.

Each year, a training and awareness-raising programme is designed and there are protocols in place with the National Institute of Administration (INA), the State Centre for Legal Skills (Jurisapp) and the Ministries' General Secretariats.

Training is legally regulated in Portugal through Law No. 86-A/2016. Although this regulation does not specify training on gender equality, but the action plan on equality between women and men 2018-2030 includes a specific objective on training as part of the strategic objective to integrate gender equality concerns into all policies and other actions.

In addition to more formal training, there have also been several key initiatives designed to raise awareness of the importance of gender-sensitive language in the government. Law No. 4/2018 of 9 February, Article 4 (which is dedicated to non-discriminatory language), states that gender impact assessments should also look at the use of non-discriminatory language in drafting standards by neutralising or minimising gender specification and using inclusive or neutral language.

5.6 Data on gender in the aggregates sector in Portugal

Regarding statistical data on gender in the aggregates sector in Portugal, in general there is a segregation of the labour market that penalises women more than men. The service sector accounts for more than two thirds of the total employed population and is mainly composed of women¹¹.

In terms of employment by sector of economic activity, it is observed that the sectors employ 4,812.3 thousand people, and in 2021 the tertiary sector will continue to play a predominant role in 2021, accounting for 72.7% of the total employed population.

When analysing the presence of employed men and women by sector of activity, it can be observed that (see Table 1):

- Out of every 100 employed women, 83 are in the tertiary sector, 16 in the secondary sector and 2 in the primary sector.
- Out of every 100 employed men, 63 are in the tertiary sector, 33 in the secondary sector and 4 in the primary sector.

Statistics on the primary sector cover the following activities: agriculture, forestry, fishing, hunting and mineral extraction.

In terms of sectors of activity, for every 10 persons employed in the primary and secondary sectors, there are 7 men for every 3 women.

Table 1: Employed population by sector of economic activity and sex, 2021 (thousands as %)

	População empregada: no total, por sexo e por grandes sectores de atividade económica, 2021						
	Total (HM)		Homens		Mulheres		
	(milhares)	Distr. percen. (%)	(milhares)	Distr. percen. (%)	(milhares)	Distr. percen. (%)	Taxa de feminização (%)
Setor primário ⁽¹⁾	130,6	2,7%	92,2	3,8%	38,3	1,6%	29,3%
Setor secundário ⁽²⁾	1 181,6	24,6%	805,7	33,2%	375,9	15,8%	31,8%
Setor terciário ⁽³⁾	3 500,1	72,7%	1 530,7	63,0%	1 969,5	82,6%	56,3%
Total	4 812,3	100,0%	2 428,6	100,0%	2 383,7	100,0%	49,5%

⁽¹⁾ Agricultura, floresta, caça, pesca e extração mineral; ⁽²⁾ Indústria transformadora e construção; ⁽³⁾ Serviços: comércio, transportes, administração pública, educação e saúde

11 INE/PORDATA (Dados consultados a 22 de agosto de 2022). <https://www.pordata.pt/>

5.7 Regulatory and institutional framework on Gender equality in France

Equality is one of the fundamental ideals underpinning the French Constitution. The principle of gender equality was introduced in the Preamble to the 1946 Constitution, which, like the 1958 Constitution, referenced the 1789 Declaration of the Rights of Man and the Citizen.

The Law on professional equality between women and men, adopted in 2000, was the first law to integrate gender equality concerns outside gender equality policy areas.

Law 2021-1774 (also known as the Rixain Law/*Loi Rixain*, after its main sponsor) has amended various laws to promote gender equality in the workplace, education and in general business practices.

The law will be implemented gradually between 2022 and 2029. Noteworthy provisions include Effective December 27, 2021, companies with 50 or more employees must provide the distribution of men and women in senior executive and board member positions as part of their economic, social and environmental reporting (BDESE) to the company's Social and Economic Committee (CSE). Since June 1, 2021, companies with 50 or more employees must disclose, on top of the global score, the values of the mandated gender-related pay equality elements that make up their overall annual PEI (previously only the overall PEI score had to be published, on the company's website). Effective March 1, 2022, companies with a PEI of less than 75 (out of 100) must also disclose corrective measures as well as targets to be achieved under gender equality plans made in consultation with the CSE. Also as of March 1, 2022, large companies (i.e., those with 1,000 or more employees) must disclose the gender composition of their senior executive staff (as defined by the Labor Code) and board members (as defined by the Commercial Code) to the Ministry of Labor (MoL). The information will be published annually on the MoL website starting March 2023. Effective December 27, 2022, salaries of employees must be paid into accounts in their name, in order to strengthen the financial independence of women. Payment of salaries into accounts solely in the name of third parties will be prohibited. Starting March 1, 2026, large companies will further be subject to gender-based quotas of at least 30% for senior executives and board members, applying to both men and women (increasing to 40% in March 2029). Employers that fail to meet the quotas must establish action plans and corrective measures in their gender equality plans. Companies that still fail to meet their quota after two years may be subject to fines of up to 1% of their annual payroll, from March 1, 2029.

France does not have a national strategy on gender equality per se.

The most important National Action Plan to date was the Inter-ministerial Plan for gender equality at work 2016-2020. The Plan aimed to combat structural inequalities between women and men in employment.

At national level, the Service for Women's Rights and Gender Equality (SDFE) is the governmental body responsible for gender equality and gender mainstreaming. It is under the responsibility of the General Directorate for Social Cohesion (Direction générale de la cohésion sociale, DGCS), located within the Ministry of Solidarity and Health.

The National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (Institut national des statistiques et des études économiques, Insee) has a webpage dedicated to gender statistics.

5.8 Gender in the aggregates sector in France

Regarding statistical data on gender in the aggregates extraction industry in France, the following data on the presence of women in the sector, compiled by the UPNG- L'Union nationale des producteurs de granulats, are given below, for every 6 employees in the materials industry, there is an average of 5 men and 1 woman.

The percentage of women in the sector amounts to 17.58% of the total, according to data collected in 2020. Of these, less than 8% are in blue-collar positions, with executive and managerial positions being the most popular for women.

Pour 6 salariés de l'industrie des matériaux, on compte en moyenne 5 hommes et une femme.

Genre des salariés* de l'Industrie des Matériaux

Unité : nombre de salariés* | Source : DADS INSEE 2019 Edition 2022 | Traitement : Réseau des CERC

17%
de femmes salariées*

* Salariés permanents hors intérim

ACTIVITÉ, EMPLOI, FORMATION DANS L'INDUSTRIE DES MATÉRIAUX EN FRANCE

11

Figure 5: Statistical data on the total percentage of women in relation to men in the materials industry sector

Figure 6: Statistics on the type of work mostly carried out by women in the sector.

6 DEQ Gender Action plan

In the design and planning phase of the DEQ GAP, the objectives, measures or actions designed to achieve them and the person or persons responsible for their achievement must be clear. Also, those indicators that will allow us to monitor its compliance and have proof of its success or failure.

The following chapter sets out the main objectives of this GAP, first, with respect to the object of the project and the methodology used, and second, with respect to gender balance within the consortium.

6.1 Gender dimension in research

Gender is considered as a key analytical and explanatory variable in research. If relevant gender issues are missed or poorly addressed, research results will be partial and potentially biased. Gender can thus be an important factor in research excellence.

Viewing women as an undifferentiated group and opposing this to men as an undifferentiated group (merely disaggregating data by sex) misses essential factors that influence gendered behaviours.

Even if technology in quarries might seem a gender-neutral issue, it is interesting to assess the interplay between gender and technology impact. Analysing gender, in this instance, means comparing women's and men's behaviours and attitudes in relation to technology innovations.

Addressing gender dimension in research means contributing to:

- Improving the scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology, and innovation.
- Upgrading the rigor, reproducibility, and generalizability of science.
- Increasing the knowledge base that will have a societal value.

6.1.1 Actions/objectives to implement in DEQ to ensure gender dimension in research

Table 2 summarizes the objectives and actions to be implemented in the project in relation to the gender dimension.

Table 2: GAP Objectives research dimension

Objectives	Actions	Calendar	WP/ Task	Responsible	KPIs
Design a research methodology that considers the gender / sex dimension	<p>Gender dimension should be addressed in a specific Work Package or Task within a work package. The gender dimension is addressed within the project in the GAP within task 10.4.</p> <p>During the conception of the Project any gender aspect that might be relevant to the Project should be considered and included in the work package specific task.</p> <p>The project must ensure an open and impartial selection procedure of people participating in the pilot sites. Diverse groups of end users should be involved in the project life-cycle to ensure inclusive solutions.</p> <p>Consider how to involve diverse end users in the project life cycle to ensure inclusive solutions.</p> <p>Research methods, such as questionnaires, focus groups, etc., should be designed in a way that considers possible sex/gender differences and similarities between gender.</p> <p>Sex/gender-differentiated data will be collected.</p>	During the entire duration of the project.	All	WP/Task leader	<p>Relevant results regarding gender / sex dimension.</p> <p>Number of tables / surveys / questionnaires disaggregated by sex/gender.</p> <p>Number of searches for the project on the internet.</p> <p>Express mentions to the GAP and the gender dimension throughout the project, in each of the deliverables.</p>

Objectives	Actions	Calendar	WP/ Task	Responsible	KPIs
	<p>Inspect the DEQ analytical concepts, categories, and theoretical models for misguided or stereotypical assumptions.</p> <p>Consider risk of stereotyping or excluding relevant groups.</p> <p>Consider how gender relations between researchers and participants may impact data collection.</p>				
<p>To raise awareness about the gender dimension within the project, its goals and actions to ensure their fulfilment.</p>	<p>Organization of face-to-face or telematic information sessions. Webinars.</p> <p>Organization of working groups, round tables.</p> <p>Sending informative emails.</p> <p>Participation of the consortium members in the preparation of the GAP and the GEP of the DEQ.</p> <p>Publication of GAP on the Project website.</p> <p>Support of the coordination of the Project to these training and participatory actions, as well as publication of commitment on the website of the Project of acceptance and compliance of the consortium of the contents included in the GAP.</p>	<p>During the entire duration of the project.</p>	All	GE Officer	<p>Number of visits/consultations to the equality banner.</p> <p>Number of emails with Gender Dimension info sent to the consortium members.</p> <p>Number of queries sent to the Gender Officer in matters of gender dimension.</p> <p>Number of publications issued by project managers or coordinators that expressly support the GAP.</p> <p>Express mentions to the GAP and the gender dimension throughout the project, in each of the deliverables.</p>
<p>To include sex/gender dimension in the dissemination phase</p>	<p>Report how information on gender identity was obtained.</p> <p>Disaggregate reported results by sex and gender.</p> <p>Ensure that gender variations are properly reported in tables, figures and conclusions.</p> <p>Avoid overemphasizing gender differences. Are the observed variations of practical significance?</p>	<p>During the dissemination phase</p>	All	WP/Task leader	<p>Number of publications in which the conclusions of the DEQ on Gender are mentioned.</p> <p>Express mentions to the GAP and the gender dimension throughout the project, in each of the deliverables.</p>

6.1.2 Gender balance in research

Within the project, a gender balance policy will be developed in the process and research that addresses the issue from the point of view of recruitment, selection, hiring and the assessment of merits. The Project must ensure an open and impartial selection procedure, as well as fair working conditions to researchers recruited.

Improving women's participation in research requires including female researchers in teams at all levels while offering gender sensitive working conditions and culture.

Three objectives underpin the European Commission's strategy on gender equality in research policy:

- Fostering equality in scientific careers.
- Ensuring gender balance in decision-making processes and bodies.
- Integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation content, i.e., considering the biological characteristics and the social features of women and men.

As laid out in the European Commission's Communication for reinforced European Research Area (2012), the EU Member States are encouraged to:

- Create a legal and policy environment and provide incentives to:
 - remove legal and other barriers to the recruitment, retention and career progression of female researchers while fully complying with EU law on gender equality (Directive 2006/54/EC).
 - address gender imbalances in decision making processes.
 - strengthen the gender dimension in research programmes.
- Engage in partnerships with funding agencies, research organisations and universities to foster cultural and institutional change on gender – charters, performance agreements, and awards.
- Ensure that at least 40% of the underrepresented sex participate in committees involved in recruitment/career progression and in establishing and evaluating research programmes.

The Council Conclusions on Advancing gender equality in the European Research (adopted in 2015) reiterate the need to foster sustainable cultural and institutional change in the ERA national action plans or strategies at the level of Member States and research institutions.

The Council also invites EU Member States and research funding organisations to provide incentives to encourage higher education institutions and research organisations to revise or develop gender mainstreaming strategies and/or gender equality plans and to mobilise adequate resources.

The Council calls for:

- Guiding targets in decision-making bodies, such as leading scientific and administrative boards, recruitment and promotion committees and evaluation panels, to achieve gender balance in leadership and decision-making positions.
- Guiding targets for a more even gender balance of full professors in higher education institutions.
- Monitoring, with appropriate indicators, the implementation of gender policies, and actions at institutional, national and EU level.
- Gender awareness-raising and capacity-building tools in order to achieve institutional change.
- Flexible and family-friendly working conditions and arrangements for both women and men.
- The review of the assessment of researchers' performance, to eliminate gender bias.

Considering all the above recommendations, the project aims to promote gender balance at all levels in DEQ teams and in management structures.

To ensure that this objective is achieved, a Gender Equality Plan inspired by the "The Code of Conduct for Recruitment" has been developed, drawn up by the European Commission, which sets out the basic principles to ensure equality and gender balance in the recruitment of researchers participating in projects financed by the Commission.

7 DEQ GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

The Equality Plan has been drawn up in a participatory process with the collaboration of the members of the consortium. The zero draft was circulated to the members of the project from 21/05/2023 until 29/05/2023, period in which comments and suggestions were collected.

The final document was circulated to all members of the consortium on 26/05/2023.

Regarding the indicators, tools have been developed in the form of Excel tables to collect data that allow to measure the degree of fulfilment of the main objective, that is, to achieve a balanced presence of women and men both in the research teams and in the Decision-making process.

The plan will be divided on the one hand in the enunciation of the principles and objectives, to later translate the measurement instruments.

Every year an analysis of the results obtained in the measurement instruments will be carried out, and the results and their evolution will be analysed.

The objectives and principles are formulated in a flexible way to allow adaptation to change.

This plan is intended to be reviewed annually.

7.1 Principles and objectives

- **Recognition:** all researchers engaged in a the DEQ Project should be recognised as professionals and be treated accordingly.
- **No discrimination:** no form of discrimination will be allowed against members of the DEQ consortium in any way based on gender, age, ethnic, national, or social origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation, language, disability, political opinion, social or economic condition.
- **Resources:** fund managers and decision makers will ensure that the most stimulating research or research training environment is created by offering appropriate equipment, facilities, and opportunities, including for remote collaboration over research networks, and that the national or sectoral regulations concerning health and safety in research are observed. Fund managers should ensure that adequate resources are provided in support of the agreed work programme.
- **Flexible working conditions:** fund managers and decision makers should ensure that the working conditions for researchers within the project provide where appropriate the flexibility deemed essential for successful research performance in accordance with existing legislation. They should aim to provide working conditions which allow both women and men researchers to combine family and work, children, and career. Particular attention should be paid, to flexible working hours, part-time working, tele-working, and sabbatical leave, as well as to the necessary financial and administrative provisions governing such arrangements.
- **Stability and permanence of employment:** fund managers and decision makers should ensure that the performance of workers involved in the DEQ Project is not undermined by instability of employment contracts and should therefore commit themselves as far as possible to improving the stability of employment conditions for the project members. Salaries should ensure that researchers enjoy fair and attractive conditions of funding and/or salaries with adequate and equitable social security provisions.
- **Gender balance:** DEQ Project should aim for a representative gender balance at all levels of staff, including at supervisory and managerial level. This should be achieved based on an equal opportunity policy at recruitment and at the subsequent career stages without, however, taking precedence over quality and competence criteria.
- **Participation in decision-making bodies:** DEQ Consortium partners should be represented in the relevant information, consultation, and decision-making bodies of the project, to protect and promote their individual and collective interests as professionals and to actively contribute to the workings of the consortium.

- **Selection procedure:** when selecting the personnel, the selection procedure should bring together diverse expertise and competences and should have an adequate gender balance and, where appropriate and feasible, include members from different sectors and disciplines. The selection shall be based on the following criteria:
 - Proven competence and experience of the individual candidate, in areas of relevance to the challenge/objective concerned.
 - Proven competence and experience of the individual candidate including cross-cutting issues of relevance to Horizon 2020.
- **Recruitment procedure:** The recruitment procedure should ensure that the entry and admission standards for researchers are clearly specified and should also facilitate access for disadvantaged groups. The recruitment procedure within the DEQ should be open, efficient, transparent, supportive, and internationally comparable. The recruitment procedure will be based on the following principles:
 - **Transparency:** Candidates should be informed, prior to the selection, about the recruitment process and the selection criteria, the number of available positions and the career development prospects. They should also be informed after the selection process about the strengths and weaknesses of their applications.
 - **Judging merit:** The selection process should take into consideration the whole range of experience of the candidates. While focusing on their overall potential as researchers, their creativity and level of independence should also be considered. This means that merit should be judged qualitatively as well as quantitatively, focusing on outstanding results within a diversified career path and not only on the number of publications. For candidates from an industrial background, particular attention should be paid to any contributions to patents, development or inventions.
 - **Variations in the chronological order of CVs:** career breaks or variations in the chronological order of CVs should not be penalised, but regarded as an evolution of a career, and consequently, as a potentially valuable contribution to the professional development of researchers towards a multidimensional career track. Candidates should therefore be allowed to submit evidence-based CVs, reflecting a representative array of achievements and qualifications appropriate to the post for which application is being made.
 - **Recognition of mobility experience:** any mobility experience, e.g., a stay in another country/region or in another research setting (public or private) or a change from one discipline or sector to another, whether as part of the initial research training or at a later stage of the research career, or virtual mobility experience, should be considered as a valuable contribution to the professional development of a researcher.
 - **Recognition of qualifications:** an appropriate assessment and evaluation of the academic and professional qualifications, including nonformal qualifications, of all researchers should be provided.
 - **Seniority:** the levels of qualifications required should be in line with the needs of the position and not be set as a barrier to entry.

7.2 Actions

- Conduct impact assessment/ audits of procedures and practices to identify gender bias.
- Implement strategies to correct/eliminate any gender bias
- Set targets and monitor progress via indicators.
- Promote the definition and implementation of policies and commitments at local level (geographies, associations, specific sectors) to favor the introduction of underrepresented groups
- Leading decision-making boards and evaluation panels, to achieve gender balance in leadership and decision-making positions.
- Monitoring, with appropriate indicators, the implementation of gender policies and actions.
- Gender awareness-raising and capacity-building tools to achieve institutional change.

- Promote flexible and family-friendly working conditions and arrangements for both women and men.
- The progress of gender balance within the consortium will be monitored and documented on an annual basis in terms of o successful female applications to DEQ open calls and of o presence of women with responsibility tasks and at senior level positions.
- In the plenary meetings, specific content on compliance with the GAP will be included during the analysis period. Within the plenary meetings, roundtables or participatory processes may be organized to improve or introduce suggestions to the objectives established in the GAP. This represents an important action for introducing a space for gender equality discussion in the regular functioning of the project and for ensuring long-term activity of the Gender Action Plan, ensuring that it adapts to the specific needs detected by the members of the consortium.
- To promote the DEQ Gender Equality Plan and to receive useful input from experts in the field, those responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the plan will actively participate in international gender-related conferences and workshops. Moreover, the participation to special sessions on gender equality in science within general scientific conference will be supported.
- A gender-balanced participation at internal meetings and workshops as well as at external conferences and publication will be promoted, supporting the dissemination of scientific results and the creation of an international network of collaboration for both male and female scientist.
- The possibility of working under flexible working hours will be supported to reconcile work and private life. Moreover, internal meetings will be planned during core working hours, and the use of teleconferencing will be strongly promoted to minimize the need for travelling.
- A direct collaboration with the equal opportunity offices at the partner sites, if existing, will be established for obtaining valuable recommendations for improving the management of gender-related issues within DEQ.
- DEQ has appointed a Gender Officer who monitors gender balance and is responsible for actively sensitizing consortium partners on gender-related aspects. He/she will ensure a continuity in the development and improvement of the GAP.
- A 1-day workshop could be organized to discuss gender balance in DEQ pilot sites and define actions to be taken especially for those members where the representation of women is still limited.
- The gender officer, together with adequate personnel at the Pilot sites, could implement an objective plan with specific timelines, including the development of incentives for partner sites to improve gender balance.

7.3 Tools for measuring compliance with the equality plan

In order to carry out adequate monitoring of the equality plan, and to be able to draw conclusions about its evolution and success, these monitoring tools have been developed that collect valuable information referred to:

- The CVs of the members of the consortium and their role within the project and in the decision-making structure.
- Existence of an equality plan within the organizations participating in the project.
- Summary table of the participation percentages of women and men in the project.

7.3.1 Skills of the members involved in the DEQ project

The skills of the initial members involved in the DEQ project have been compiled in an internal file. The purpose is to evaluate their skills and study them in relation to gender. As personal and confidential information, it will be used in future aggregated analyses, in compliance with data protection laws. These assessments covered job-related competencies crucial for the DEQ project's success.

Strict confidentiality measures were implemented to safeguard the personal information of project members. Access to the collected data was restricted to authorized personnel, ensuring confidentiality and privacy.

Collected data will be securely stored, with any identifying information anonymized or removed. The aggregated data will be used for future analyses, studying skill distribution by gender. These analyses aim to identify patterns or discrepancies that may require further investigation or targeted interventions. Our data collection and analysis strictly adhere to applicable data protection laws. Privacy and confidentiality of personal information are maintained, complying with legal requirements.

Figure 7: Cvs of partner role's

Partner	Person	Gender	WF	Task	GA	Qualification	Current Position	Experience
ANEFA	César Luaces Frades	Male		Project Coordinator		Doctor Mining Engineer from the Higher Technical School of Mining of Oviedo (Principado de Asturias, Spain) Master Degree in Environment Impact Assessment (Malaga University) 1997 Master in Management of Business Associations - Korazza - (2010 - 2011) Studies in Master in Business Administration - Comillas Pontifical University - ICADE (Studies completed - not titled) - (2001 - 2002) Master Studies in Occupational Risk Prevention - Center for Financial Studies (Studies completed- not titled) (1999 - 2000) 108 courses and seminars in Spain, related to the areas of Mining, Quarrying, business economics, sector strategy, environment, safety and health, quality of aggregates, management systems, information and communication technologies, management, lobby, etc. 53 courses and seminars abroad (14 countries in Europe and America), related to the areas of Mining, Quarrying, business economics, sector strategy, environment, quality of aggregates, management, etc.	Director General of ANEFA Director General of the Federación de Áridos – FDA (The Spanish Aggregates Federation) Secretary General of The Confederación Española de Industrias Extractivas de Rocas y Minerales Industriales – COMINROC (Spanish Confederation of extractive industries of rock and industrial minerals) Director General of PRIMIGEA - Confederación Española de las Industrias de las Materias Primas Minerales (Spanish Confederation of Mineral Raw Materials Industries) Honorary Director General of the Iberoamerican Aggregates Federation – FIPA Member of the board of European Aggregates Association – UEPG Chair of the Health and Safety Committee of UEPG, of the Water Management Task Force and many other technical groups at European level Chair of the Sectoral Social Dialogue Committee for the Extractive Industries (SSDCEI) Participant in several Committees and WG of the European Commission on behalf of UEPG	He is author of more than 100 publications related to the aggregates sector. He has written a considerable number of articles that have been published in media, and he has actively participated in approximately 1,000 conferences and presentations in different congress in a national level as well as international. Coordination and development of about 100 technical projects related with aggregates industry.
ANEFA	Rosa Carretón Moreno	Female		Technical coordination		Mining Engineer from the Higher Technical School of Mining and Energy Engineers in Madrid, at the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Spain	Technical manager of ANEFA	She has been working since 2007 as technical manager of ANEFA, where she has published different studies. She has extensive experience in the management of mining engineering projects, and the management of the human resources needed for mining, as well as the prevention of labour risks associated with the aggregates industry.
ANEFA	Rita Martínez Andía	Female		Environmental coordination		Bch. Environmental Risk Management by the San Valero School of Higher Education in Zaragoza, Spain	Environmental manager of ANEFA	She has been working since 2010 as environmental manager of ANEFA, where she has published different studies. She has extensive experience in the management of mining engineering projects, and the management of the human resources needed for mining, as well as the environmental risks associated with the aggregates industry.
ANEFA	María Loeck de Lapuerta	Female		Economic and Social acceptance coordination		Bachelor degree in law an business from University Pontificia de Comillas ICADE (2007-2012) MSc in Compliance Officer from Complutense University in Madrid (2019-2020)	Head of Legal and Economic Coordination and Compliance Officer of ANEFA	Having previously worked as a labour lawyer, since joining ANEFA she has developed the role of head of Legal and Economic Coordination of the Association, performing legal and economic advisory work in multiple areas. Furthermore, she has actively participated in Spanish and European projects such as the H2020 project "Ageing at Work", in which ANEFA participates as one of the pilot sites. As Compliance Officer she has led and developed ANEFA's ethical and regulatory compliance program and is currently developing a guide for the implementation of compliance in the aggregates sector.

Collected data will be securely stored, with any identifying information anonymized or removed. The aggregated data will be used for future analyses, studying skill distribution by gender. These analyses aim to identify patterns or discrepancies that may require further investigation or targeted interventions. Our data collection and analysis strictly adhere to applicable data protection laws. Privacy and confidentiality of personal information are maintained, complying with legal requirements.

7.3.2 Gender policy in place

It established a registry dedicated to documenting organisations that have successfully implemented approved gender policies within their respective workplaces. This registry aims to recognise and celebrate organisations that priorities gender equality, fostering inclusive and supportive environments.

The registry was created through involved stakeholder engagement and information gathering from organisations. By showcasing these organisations, the registry promotes transparency and accountability regarding gender policies. It serves as a valuable resource, inspiring other entities to implement similar initiatives and contributing to a broader culture of gender equality in the workplace. Figure 8 shows the results of the gender policy per partner.

Partner	Gender policy in place Yes or No	If yes, please date of approval
ANEFA	Yes	12/2/21
VICAT		
Hanson		
Holcim		
CSI		
CIMPOR		
SANDVIK		
Metso		
Maxam		
ITK		
MUL	Yes	22/12/21
CHALMERS		
UPM	Yes	26/1/23
Akkodis	Yes	1/11/22
ARCO		
MESTRO		
DOHMEN		
ABAUT		
APP		
SIGMA		
DGASTUR		
ASOGRAVAS		
MINTEK		
ZABALA		
ROCTIM		

Figure 8: Answers of gender policy in place

The registry provides numerous benefits, such as guiding individuals seeking employment in organisations that priorities gender equality and facilitating knowledge sharing among organisations. By documenting and recognising these organisations, we hope to encourage more entities to prioritise gender equality, creating work environments that are inclusive, diverse, and supportive of all. The registry stands as a testament to the progress made and a catalyst for positive change in promoting gender equality within organisations.

7.3.3 Summary

The current item provides an update on the representation of women in the project Figure 9. However, it is important to note that the data presented here is based on the available information at this point, which includes the people involved in the proposal writing and the first reporting period of the project (from the start of the project until month 18, November 2022).

Evolution of female hires during the 1PR

Figure 9 Evolution of female hires during the 1PR.

According to the initial proposal, there were 34 women involved in the project. However, in the first reporting period, the partners have informed that they are currently working with 77 (+43 hired women) women, representing a significant increase in female hiring across all the partners involved in the project.

It is worth mentioning that only 3 out of the 25 partners have reported a decrease in the number of women involved. These two partners have very small teams, so any variation in the number of employees has a significant impact. Despite this, the overall trend shows a considerable increase in the hiring of women in the project, which is an encouraging sign of progress towards gender equality in the workplace.

8 Conclusions

Gender is considered as a key analytical and explanatory variable in research. If relevant gender issues are missed or poorly addressed, research results will be partial and potentially biased. Gender can thus be an important factor in research excellence.

Even if technology in quarries might seem a gender-neutral issue, it is key to address gender dimension in research. It means contributing to improving the scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology, and innovation; upgrading the rigor, reproducibility, and generalizability of science; and increasing the knowledge base that will have a societal value.

The DIGIECOQUARRY INNOVATIVE DIGITAL SUSTAINABLE AGGREGATES SYSTEMS, DEQ, aims to design, develop, and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) that comprises sensors, processes, tools and data capture, processing, and exchange methods to provide integrated, digitized information, control of automatic and real-time processes for aggregate quarries.

Even though when stating the objectives of the project, it could be concluded that it is an issue in which the gender dimension is irrelevant, from the project's conception, the gender dimension has been considered as one of its fundamental elements. In the conviction that only in a research process that involves the gender dimension, socially relevant results can be achieved, and in accordance with article 33 of our GA, the DEQ Project has developed this Gender Action Plan in accordance with the Commission's recommendations.

Gender equality plans and gender management plans are relatively new concepts that are constantly changing and evolving. A research effort has been made to analyse the regulatory and institutional framework in relation to the issue of gender and equality, in the countries where the pilots will be carried out.

In addition, quality statistical data on sex and gender within the aggregates sector that could be obtained from some countries (Spain, Portugal and France) have been included in the document.

These data lead us to conclude that although gender and equality politics are fundamental in all EU countries with a clear progressive development and institutional and regulatory support, the aggregates sector, due to its special nature as a sector mainly composed of small and medium-sized companies, and traditionally masculine, the gender issue is not a priority, while the female presence is scarce or null and practically relegated to administrative or managerial positions. In most cases, companies will not have gender equality plans and there will be no awareness of their usefulness or necessity.

In this scenario, the construction of this Gender Action plan, in addition to being a challenge, becomes an opportunity, insofar as the female role in mining can be analysed in different pilot scenarios throughout Europe and solutions can be proposed to improve gender dimension, resulting in benefits for the sector.

The GAP has set itself two basic objectives: on the one hand, to establish tools to ensure that gender is considered in the research, and on the other, that there is a gender balance in the composition of research teams and decision-making teams.

To achieve these objectives, a Gender Equality Plan has been drawn up, inspired by the European Commission's Recruitment Code of Conduct, which establishes a series of principles and objectives and tools for measuring compliance with the Equality Plan.

Throughout the process of elaboration of this GAP, Consortium members have actively collaborated in its elaboration, enriching the gender analysis with their data, and contributing to the plan conformation.

There is a clear awareness of the importance of the gender and equality in research and of gender balance in the research team and in decision making processes.

From the data obtained, we can conclude a positive trend towards a greater gender balance, with an increasing presence of women in research and decision-making teams.

This GAP is a living document that will need to be monitored and updated as the DEQ progresses.

The next review of this GAP will take place one year from the presentation of deliverable 10.4, without prejudice to the fact that in the event of significant changes, either regulatory or institutional, or within the project, a timely update will be made.

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List of Figures

Figure 1 Women miners in quarries.....	11
Figure 2 DEQ GAP phases.....	15
Figure 3 Active Population Survey (EPA) Source, National Institute of Statistics. SPAIN 2021.....	18
Figure 4 Gender evolution in mining. Source Mining Statistics 2017.....	19
Figure 5: Statistical data on the total percentage of women in relation to men in the materials industry sector.....	23
Figure 6: Statistics on the type of work mostly carried out by women in the sector.....	23
Figure 7: Cvs of partner role's.....	30
Figure 8: Answers of gender policy in place.....	31
Figure 9 Evolution of female hires during the 1PR.....	32

List of Tables

Table 1: Employed population by sector of economic activity and sex, 2021 (thousands as %)..... 21

Table 2: GAP Objectives research dimension 24